

ACADEMIC STRESS AND SELF ESTEEM OF TRIBAL SCHOOL ADOLESCENT GIRLS IN KERALA

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Abstract

An inclusive social, physical and emotional environment invites the marginalized and those divorced from normal life even with an opportunity for retaining whatever is indigenous to a certain extent. But a child from the marginalized group is prone to many psychological problems and dissatisfaction and academic stress has been identified as a major condition of the mind which demands a comfort zone in school, family and society. Disparity in educational attainment between scheduled caste and scheduled communities has been identified in Kerala context. Researches, policies, recommendations, programmes, schemes and discussions are plenty on the theme of tribal education in India, especially in Kerala, the land occupied by 4 lakh tribes of different groups. The dire need for a research on self-esteem and academic stress of scheduled tribe students who represent the most disadvantaged sections of the society could be felt from the exhaustive theoretical understanding and review of related studies. Recognizing the intervening effects of self esteem and academic stress on the overall educational process of the representatives of the future youth of the nation, a study on Academic Stress and Self Esteem of Tribal School Adolescent Girls in Kerala has been undertaken. The paper discusses the details of the survey study carried out among a stratified random sample of 120 tribe adolescent girl students with the objective to find out the correlation between their academic stress and self esteem, using the tools academic stress scale and self esteem inventory.

Key words: academic stress; self-esteem; tribe girl students

Introduction

What lies behind us and what lies before us are

Tiny matters compared to what lies within us (Emerson)

Today, human race, on the information super high way is heading towards victory, moment by moment, and is in merriment of its achievements over the physical world. Moreover we claim to be victorious when we take on loan, the joys and opportunities of our fellow beings and continue to boast, about the achievements over 'the deprived'. Everybody agrees that modern industrial society suffers from erosion of human hood. Personal and public evils at the cost of human security and comfort facilitate an unwelcomed increase in the global temperature. The marginalized feel more and more dissatisfied, deprived and divorced from normal life even without being aware that there is a universe of beings similar to them who are crazy towards praise, power and position. Every child has the right to right knowledge and right living. But when we could read on Black magic and Whats App with the same cup of tea, we should recognize the gap in the quality of education that the different sections of the society are exposed to.

We should grow up with ability to analyze not only our life space but that of our near ones, the immediate community, the state, the nation as well as the universe. But when it is reported by the World Bank, "high-caste teachers boycotted the attempted change in the status of low-caste individuals" (The Hindu, December 15, 2014), let's salute the empathy that flows through the high caste blood vessels of Medha Padkar to join the five-month stand-up agitation by the *Adivasis* in Kerala in 2014. The unique land of unity in diversity bears the second largest concentration of God's own people - the tribes - who still remain as the most disadvantaged.

Need and Significance of the study

Biological and sociological interpretations of gender differences and active discrimination based on caste are critical hampers in India's social, economic, political development. Neo-Freudian psychoanalysts believe that an individual begins his life with certain potential and two basic goals of life: satisfaction and security. In the process of education, an infant from one 'big blooming confusion' transforms into the eventual adult state of consciousness, his physical and mental characteristics take shape and he starts reflecting on them - thus developing his self concept. One starts evaluating the discrepancy between self-image and ideal self. Self esteem is the "affective evaluation" of this discrepancy. A child with high self-esteem is likely to be confident in social situations and in tackling school work. In spite of the financial and human support to the marginalized sections of Indian society, they continue to be 'unwilling to change, to develop'. Still, opportunities are related to caste and class within Indian social structure. (Scaria, 2014). Disparity in educational attainment between scheduled caste and scheduled communities has been identified in Kerala context (Kanna & Raveendran, 2011). It has already been reported in a survey that the custom of untouchability still exists among the upper castes, especially the Brahmin communities in India. More surveys on needs and problems of scheduled tribe children and their community have been suggested by Panda and Laxmidhar (2011). Again, wide intra-group inequalities are detected among different sub-groups of the tribal community itself. The Dream of India could never imbibe life if the marginalized group is not assured access to quality education in a safe environment, a safe academic environment.

Researches, policies, recommendations, programmes, schemes and discussions are plenty on the theme of tribal education in India, especially in Kerala, the land occupied by 4 lakh tribes of different groups. Research studies in Education, Sociology and Anthropology have brought to light certain thrust areas to be accounted for, while planning for the uplift of the marginalized. The themes of alienation, discrimination and abuse (Vikram, 2014) lack of self-confidence, lack of motivation and lack of scaffold and stereotyping by the society, the school, the teacher and the peers have been identified as primary areas to be remedied.

Even when tribal schools in Kerala claim improved infrastructure facilities, research studies (Abdurahman (2011), Kishu and Sasikala (2011), Barran, Thymothi and Smith (2007), and Divya (2011) say that problems related to psychological, economic, familial and personal are abundant. The philosophy of knowing every child and then facilitating him meaningfully could be meaningful only when the child knows and realizes himself. Panda & Behera (2011) have recommended strategies to boost self-esteem and self-identity among scheduled tribe students at secondary school level.

. A child from the marginalized group and the society is prone to many psychological problems and dissatisfaction and academic stress has been identified as a major condition of the mind which invites the establishment of a comfort zone in school, family and society. Even tribal school teachers experience stress and they have to develop proximal curriculum transaction skills to 'downsize the stressful situation through stress proofing tactics'. (Sudharma & Lekshmi, 2011). Academic stress is developed among Scheduled tribe students on the main factors related to family, school, teacher and examination. The association between self esteem and stress was studied among adolescent boys and girls of 12-18 years, by Gir, S, Sharma, S., & Upathyay, B. (2011). Of the 480 sample, those with low self-esteem were found to have high stress. A study with a psycho social learning perspective could bring to light the barriers that the scheduled tribe students have to overcome and more importantly, the strategies that the authorities have to follow for their academic issues. .

The dire need for a research on self-esteem and academic stress of scheduled tribe students who represent the most disadvantaged sections of the society could be felt from the exhaustive theoretical understanding and review of related studies. The studies have been carried out either in the general stream of education or are focused on general issues of scheduled caste and scheduled tribe students problems of tribal school students also have been investigated but in the Kerala context studies couldn't be located on the selected variables. Recognizing the intervening effects of self esteem and academic stress on the overall educational process of the representatives of the future youth of the nation, the present study on Academic Stress and Self Esteem of Tribal School Adolescent Girls in Kerala has been undertaken.

Statement of the problem

The problem is titled as, "Academic Stress and Self Esteem of Tribal School Adolescent Girls in Kerala". The present study is to find the levels of academic stress and self esteem of the tribal school students. The two variables in the study on Academic stress and Self Esteem of Tribal School Adolescent Girls in Kerala are self-esteem and academic stress. Self esteem is "the judgment and attitude an individual holds towards self". (Good, 1973).Academic stress is the product of a combination of academic related demands that exceed the adaptive resources available to an individual (Wilks,2008).It is the stress developed due to school, family, curriculum, academic environment and personal stressors related to academic environment. Tribal Schools are Secondary Schools where more than fifty percentage of admission is exclusive to tribe students.

Academic Stress

For a learner, the most harming stress originates from the school, peers, teachers and family. The sources can be the curriculum, the examination or the evaluation system. Stress develops on the learner's own perception of his academic achievements. There are various approaches to stress and theories also. General Adaptation Theory of Selye, Person Environment Fit Theory of French (1982) Transactional Stress Theory etc are commonly accepted. The problems have been categorized as those related to learner, teacher and school, learning resources and socio-cultural background.

Self Esteem

The concept of self-esteem has been explained by all the theorists synonymously.The recent researches indicate that self-esteem could be artificially boosted and the findings scaffold the ventures of National Association for self-esteem is U.S and the self-esteem movement of David Hume.Maurao Rodringuez came up with a theory of self-esteem with three stages of development: self concept, self respect and self knowledge.Along with the three stages of development of self-esteem, five factors identified by Rodriguez are: Resilience, Assertiveness, Values, Free Time and Life Project

Objectives of the study

- (i) To find out the extent of academic stress of tribal school adolescent girls in Kerala.
- (ii) To find out the extent of self-esteem of tribal school adolescent girls in Kerala.
- (iii) To find out the correlation between academic stress and self esteem of tribal school adolescent girls in Kerala.

Methodology in Brief

For the present study, an appropriate methodology was formulated with a back up of an in-depth review of related literature.

Method

To find answers to the set objectives of the study, survey method was followed.

Sample

The required data were collected from a sample of one hundred and twenty tribal school students from the Model Residential Higher Secondary Schools, Model Residential High Schools and Ashram Schools.. Since the total population is tribal school students in Kerala is below 2000, stratified random sampling technique was applied to give due representation to gender.

Tools for data collection

Data on self esteem of tribal school students were collected using Self Esteem Inventory constructed by the investigators. Academic Stress Scale (Jesa, 2014) is the tool developed to collect data on academic stress. The tool self esteem inventory was constructed and standardized following the steps systematically. The reliability coefficient obtained was 0.73. The criterion validity was established and the correlation coefficient was 0.78. The face validity was ensured by selecting appropriate statements to measure self esteem of tribal school adolescent girls. The components of academic stress considered for the development of the Academic stress scale were: family stressors, school stressors, curriculum stressors and personal stressors. The adopted scale has fifty items and is a three point The scale with three responses: to a great extent, to some extent and not at all. The reliability of the tool is 0.81 and content validity is established. There are 49 statements in the final tool including negative statements.

Data Collection Procedure

The population for the study was students of Tribal schools in Kerala. Data were collected from the selected sample from tribal schools. The tools used for collecting data were Academic stress scale and Self Esteem Inventory. Both the tools were standardized. With proper introduction regarding the purpose of data, the tools were administered

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained from 220 samples on self-esteem and academic stress were analysed to find answers to the objectives of the study. The techniques applied for analysis were: Percentage and Pearson Product Moment Correlation

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

The data collected on the two variables in the study: academic stress and self esteem were statistically analyzed and interpreted to meet the objectives of the study.

Preliminary Analysis

Descriptive analysis was carried out with the collected data to see the nature of the data and the skewness and kurtosis values were found. The values obtained on the variable academic stress show normal distribution. For self esteem, kurtosis is 0.69 and 0.77 while those for academic stress are -0.39 and 0.33. The data could be statistically analyzed and interpreted for generalization.

Level of Academic Stress of Tribal Secondary School Girls

The levels of total academic stress were high, moderate and low. The percentage distribution is given in Table 1

TABLE 1

Level of Academic Stress

Level	Percentage
High	16.36
Moderate	63.64
Low	20.00

63.64% were experiencing moderate level of academic stress while 20% was at low level. High stress was found among 16.30% .

Level of Academic Stressors Related to Family, School, Curriculum and Personal Stressors

Total academic stressors were categorized into four: family, school, curriculum, personal. The different levels and the corresponding percentages are shown in Table 2, **Levels of Academic Stressors**

Stressors	Level	Percentage
Family	High	20.45
	Moderate	58.18
	Low	21.36
Personal	High	20.91
	Moderate	59.55
	Low	19.55
School	High	22.27
	Moderate	54.55
	Low	23.18
Curriculum	High	31.82
	Moderate	29.55
	Low	38.64
Academic Environment	High	15.00
	Moderate	66.36
	Low	18.64

Stressors related to family, school, academic environment and personal stressors had some similarity in that the highest percentages fall at the moderate level. In the case of curriculum stressor only 29.55 lie at the moderate level when 38.64% showed low stress. 31.82% showed high stress related to the component. It is also seen that the percentage of high and low levels in the case of the first group of stressors are more or less equal.

Level of Self Esteem of Tribal Secondary School Girls

The percentage of the sample that experienced the three levels: high, moderate and low were found out. Data are presented in Table 3

TABLE 3

Levels of self-esteem

Level	Percentage
High	11.36
Moderate	68.64
Low	20.00

Table reads that only 11.36% possess high self esteem, 68.64% fall at the moderate level and 20% at the low level.

Correlation between Academic Stress and Self Esteem

To find the correlation between academic stress and self esteem, coefficient of correlation was calculated.

The values are presented in Table 4

TABLE 4

Coefficient of Correlation between academic stress and self esteem

N	r	SEr	Confidence interval at
220	-0.649	0.039	-0.548 to -0.075

From Table4 it is interpreted that there is significant negative correlation between academic stress and self esteem.

Results and Discussion

(i) Among the five components of academic stress, curricular stressors need maximum attention. Majority lies either at the high or at the moderate levels. The number of subjects of study and examinations generate stress.

(ii) With respect to school stressors, about 75% of students were shown to be either at the high or moderate level. Location of the school, lack of freedom of expression and lack of peer and teacher relations cause such stress. The findings indicate that the 'connectivism' in school functioning must be promoted and the teacher must be ready for a pro active change keeping aloof their pre conceptions about tribes in general.

(iii) Related to school stressors, the academic environment showed no difference and for 80%, the environment was not conducive. Gender discrimination was one serious factor and the philosophy, curriculum, methodology of all programmes must address this issue, especially by communicating the message to teachers and parents. Lack of extrinsic motivation is a negative effect of gender bias.

(iv) The 80% of students experiencing high or moderate level of personal stressors indicate that the parents, teachers, school community and the Government should reach the heart of the problems and

come up with techniques to develop problem solving ability, self expression, self confidence, goal setting and communication skills.

(v) Family generated stress was found to be high in 20.45% and moderate in 58.18%. This again points to the added responsibilities of the school, teacher community and the Government to be in continuous contact with the tribe family member. Lack of freedom, household duties, gender discrimination, lack of study facilities, illiteracy of parents, lack of motivation stand on the way and may lead to high dropout rate. Surveys have shown a marked decrease in the dropout rates. Still, stress related to family must be pulled down.

(vi) A lack of self image, self worth, self confidence, self control lead to the finding that only 11.36% had a high level of self esteem. Moderate level was shown by 68.64% also. Through direct and indirect means, self esteem must be developed. The nature of the programmes must be in tune with the social, cultural, psychological background of tribal students.

(vii) Academic stress is found to be in significant negative correlation with self esteem. All forms of stressors must be removed to the extent possible. At the same time measures to improve self esteem among the deprived sections must be adopted.

Suggestive Measures

Sensitivity to tribal culture and life, recognition of cognitive strength of tribal children and appreciation of their personality qualities are the minimum pre requisites for addressing tribal education. Being non judgmental of the child and accepting his personality as such will help the introverts establish social relationships without being defensive. An attitudinal and behavioral change is expected of the authorities in this regard. Education should recognize and respect the socio cultural and economic life style and should have a positive outlook. People's levels of achievement are influenced by how they feel about themselves to enhance self esteem," a warm relationship network is to be created."(Lawrence, 1996). Schools should provide a conducive, free study environment for the emotional and social well being to reduce the dropout rate. Frequent official visits, supervision and survey on the functioning of such schools will favour continued growth. A flexible time schedule will account for the agricultural and household chores. Curriculum must be culturally sensitive and it should not stand apart from the traditional context of the target group. A creative link must be established among culture, curriculum, pedagogy and the text. Traditional knowledge, contextualized pedagogy enriched with IT resources will attract the learners to the learning processes. The theory of connectivity which speaks for the intimate relationship among the teacher, learner and the curriculum is highly applicable for a tribal school teacher. Classes on health care, cleanliness, food habits etc can be organized by schools in collaboration with *grama sabhas* and *mahila samitis*. The Guidance and Counseling Cells in tribe schools must function with the special motto of upbringing the learners and retaining them with the school system. A school-community interface will make the schooling meaningful. Co-operation among schools and administrative bodies of the three tier system as well as NGO's should inculcate a pro-tribal attitude through inclusion.

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